

DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY IN AEROSPACE. PARAMETRIC MODELLING OF COMPLEX STRUCTURE SYSTEMS INCLUDING ACTIVE COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT: New material and technology developments allow and ask for integral and multi-scale design. The availability of advanced polymer composites and active materials offers new design concepts to the aerospace industry. However, integral design and analysis methods are not yet available to explore the potential in an economical viable way. The study of aircraft fuselages shows that further integration of mechanical and physical design solutions is possible and offers potential weight and cost savings. The use of active materials for active noise control in specific areas of the aircraft is shown to be feasible. The concept of Design and Engineering Engines will facilitate the design with these new materials.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge Based Engineering, Aircraft fuselage design, Active materials

INTRODUCTION

In the second half of last century, an explosive development of engineering materials has taken place. In not more than 35 years, the designer of aircraft and spacecraft was given a broad choice of materials each with its own advantages and disadvantages, characteristics and potential. In addition developments have and are taking place that allow the designer to overcome some shortcomings of materials and/or improve the performance of structures made from these materials, the so-called smart or active materials.

The development of materials that can be tailored and combined with active materials allows and asks for more integration of material, structure and control system development and application. The industry involved in sports and luxury cars, aircraft and other advanced and expensive transport systems can afford the application of complex control technology. The integration of computer based flight control in aircraft is standard in large civil transport and military aircraft. The use of active suspension, anti-dive systems in cars and gust alleviation systems for aircraft are some examples of these applications. These applications, however, do not yet include active materials and structures.

The increasing complexity of these new aircraft and spacecraft materials and structures asks for better control in the product development phase. The general application of the concurrent engineering approach in the aircraft development companies together with the higher interaction between disciplines due to more integral design asks for new design support tools. In this respect the development of the design process (see figure 1) and its organization will have to follow the trends in production organizations where lean manufacturing and supply chain or value chain management have become major issues of concern. The aircraft industry is extending the supply chain boundaries by incorporating the design and build philosophy. This complicates the design process by adding to the necessary demand for concurrent engineering also the demand for controlled multi-site activities since outsourcing design activities cannot be always handled through collocated teams. The current fulfillment of the need for addressable financial and intellectual resources through this design and build strategy is however of paramount importance for risk mitigation. In addition the design process as such should be restructured to reduce lead-time and have a considerable jump in productivity in the engineering effort. Only in this way the development and

introduction costs of the new materials technology can be controlled and acceptable returns on investment achieved.

Fig.1: design process [1]

progress in material technology. For example in the design of the airbus A380 the application of new

Fig. 2: the design cube

development of the material and the development of the aircraft are concurrent but of different scale. And although the costs related to the material development as such are low compared to the overall aircraft development costs, the risk on aircraft program level related to the material development are huge. This risk becomes bigger and therefore less acceptable when the materials being developed differ in a larger extent from existing material solutions, as in the case of smart material technology.

Risk assessment can be improved by more reliable predictions especially if cost and lead-time of these predictions are reduced. This can be obtained through application of Knowledge Based Engineering.

In this paper we will first look at aircraft fuselages in relation to material developments. Secondly we will look at developments in design and engineering tools for integrated design. This subject will be illustrated with an example of a so-called multi-model generator for use in the aircraft design analysis phase. Finally we will look at a specific development in the field of active material application, namely the application of piezo-electric actuators and sensors for active noise reduction.

The distributed design and the trend to fewer-but-longer development projects, as seen in e.g. military aircraft, ask for knowledge management beyond resource management as applied today. Decoupling of knowledge and knowledge workers by application of IT-tools is a promising approach in this respect. In this paper the application of Knowledge Based Engineering to improve productivity in the modeling and analysis phase of the product development are discussed. These phases are the more laborious ones and determine to a large extent the lead-time and the costs of the development process.

Current aircraft fuselage development and to a larger extent future aircraft design depends on

performance (weight and maintenance costs) with respect to existing design since, as such, the configuration of this aircraft is not driven by new technology on the aircraft configuration level. The success of the aircraft therefore relies partially on controlled development and partially on the application of new materials. For evolutionary progress this will be increasingly the case. The risk and improved management of this risk can be better understand if the three major aspects of design are understood. The design process is multi-disciplinary, multi-scale and multi-phase (see figure 2). In case of new materials application in existing aircraft configurations the risks are quite different from the case in which configurations are extended but realized with existing materials. In the former case the

AIRCRAFT FUSELAGES

The development of new materials like fiber reinforced polymers and the so-called smart or adaptive materials are leading to a new era in aircraft design. New technology is expected to support and combine with old-but-mature technology and the current metal monoculture is finally changing to a multi-culture one (see figure 3).

Fig. 3: multi-cultural design [Production Technology, TU Delft]

Fig. 4: the aluminium stiffened skin structure S-curve [3]

(see figure 6). Today the A380 is expected to show broad application of composites on the wing structure. However, the full development of a composite fuselage concept, including

The requirements list for aircraft fuselages combines high structural demands with climate control and ergonomic requirements and makes it a very multi-disciplinary design object, which is naturally suitable for an integral design approach.

The all-metal, stressed skin structure is the current standard in the transport aircraft industry. This type of structure is an (over)-optimized stiffened skin structure, for which only extensive protection measures, inspection programs and maintenance programs, can guarantee the required comfort, reliability and durable safety level. Figure 4 shows that the level of maturity of such a concept has reached its maximum and the costs of further optimisation attempts will barely follow a reasonable ROI.

Airlines are facing a continuous decrease in profit per aircraft seat (see figure 5), mainly due to the increase in competition due to the open-skies-policy and the increased cost of personnel, airports and fuel. To give the development of aircraft structures a new impulse, new combinations of materials (including active components) and structural concepts will have to be looked for and accompanying changes in manufacturing technology have to be developed. The large aircraft industry has made attempts to jump to a new S-curve to improve performance vs. unit cost. An evolutionary process has started to promote the use of composites in different aircraft locations. In case of the Airbus family aircraft, the use of fiber reinforced polymers in primary structure has started with the A310 vertical tail plane

Fig. 5: yield per passengers versus price per seat

active components, will probably still take a long time [4].

For the slow introduction of new materials and technologies in the civil aircraft industry several reasons can be identified by comparing the present situation in aviation to the introductory period of e.g. metal structures:

- In the last few decades aviation has scaled up rapidly and modern air travel has become an ordinary, common way of public transport like busses and trains. It cannot allow itself risky experiments with new materials and technologies. The phase-in period of a new technology, therefore, has become very long.
- New structural solutions have to compete with the current metal structure, which has become very efficient itself after a long period of development. Moreover, the current production systems are dedicated to the metal technology. The price of change is not easily paid without a real prospect of immediate reduction of production and operational costs.
- In the twenties the production techniques and joining methods for thin aluminium sheets were available. The manufacturing processes for new materials and technologies have to be developed first. Thermoset based composites are created simultaneously with the structure, which has complicated the development of manufacturing processes considerably.
- In the introductory period of metals, there was no well-defined safe design philosophy. It was developed simultaneously and in strong relation with the metal structures themselves. Composites are now confronted with this well-established safety philosophy and related requirements. These requirements, however, are typically metal based and, therefore, cannot simply be applied to composites.

Part of the above-mentioned risks for the industry, related to the introduction of new technology, can be reduced by use of improved methodologies to support the analysis of potential new solutions. New design and engineering methods, combined with tools developed in the field of artificial intelligence, can help to achieve this goal. In the following section, the knowledge based engineering (KBE) methodology will be discussed in more detail. It will be shown that the KBE potential goes beyond its current scope of application and it candidates for successful application also in the field of conceptual design and technology assessment.

Fig. 6: evolution of composite material application at Airbus [2]

KNOWLEDGE BASED ENGINEERING

Various design tools are used to support the different stages of the design process. To make a categorisation of these tools possible, it is important to define the basic steps of the design process as it is regarded in the current context: specification, synthesis, analysis, evaluation and design recording. For each of these steps various tools are being used and developed, which can have different appearances: they can be methods and data, presented in forms or handbooks; they can be software for recording and analysis, like CAD programs and CFD software; they can also be humans being consulted (the experts). Each tool can be considered a substantiation of design supporting knowledge. All tools together, added to

the specific knowledge and craftsmanship of the design team, complete the knowledge base for the design work. Knowledge based engineering is a modern approach for the compilation of knowledge required in a product development process. It aims to the identification, record and re-use of engineering knowledge, by combining Artificial Intelligence techniques, IT tools and Object-Oriented methodologies.

The main idea is to capture the engineering knowledge and formalise it in set of re-usable rules. When these rules are applied to different sets of data, new instantiations of the knowledge are generated in support of new products design.

In this way families of products (classes) can be defined in rules, and family members can be generated (instantiated) automatically, based on a given input data set. Many case studies of such application of the KBE methodology are now available for products of different complexity [5]. In the aerospace industry the KBE applications are generated inside the integrator companies, as well as subcontractor level, mainly for detail engineering purposes. This way of working has already proven itself to be highly effective in terms of cost reduction and lead time reduction. However, in most cases, this way of working does not yet help to exploit professional skills and free intellectual resources for improved creativity. It mainly automates repetitive activities in the detail-engineering phase by very useful cost reduction, which eliminates the need for the western world to search for low cost engineering capability in low-cost countries.

The potential of knowledge based engineering, however, is much bigger and should be exploited to approach the challenges mentioned earlier. A proper application of KBE in the conceptual and preliminary aircraft design phase can free intellectual resources for knowledge creation instead of only knowledge application. In the next section, an initial application of this concept will be discussed.

KBE IN CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

CAD systems are the most widely applied computer support tools applied in the synthesis phase of the design process. They are generic tools that can be used to create a geometric model of the design and perform some basic engineering analysis on such a model. Current generations of CAD systems are mainly feature based, which means that they have a standard set of parameterized primitives (points, lines, solid volumes, holes, chamfers etc.) that can be tuned and combined to represent a design. The knowledge recording capability and related learning capability of these systems are very limited. A CAD system can output models, which are human driven record of the geometric results of a fully human centered design process. Their simple primitives are the main limitation in that respect. Feature based modeling is a nice technique in the detail design phase that can be coupled very successfully with earlier discussed knowledge based engineering principles. However, on a higher level of abstraction the feature-based approach is too primitive to capture the knowledge behind complex products. For a CAD program an aircraft wing will always be a set of surfaces and solids, never, for instance, a lift generating object compiled of different wing sections with leading and trailing edge devices and an internal structural concept. However, if one looks at the work of the conceptual aircraft designer, it is this global modeling approach that is looked for, not a primitive feature based approach. When the conceptual designer wants a geometric representation of his ideas he would like his knowledge based engineering design environment to create this geometric model and generate the corresponding CAD drawings. All the design elements and attributes, which do not have a geometrical nature, immediately fall out the typical CAD domain. Even the generation and display of geometrical features step out the CAD capability, when the process that assesses the design topology is based on reasoning and logic statements. E.g. a parametric CAD can move and modify a given feature (i.e. a hole), build pattern with it, but it is not able to change that feature in a different feature and/or eventually modify the complete product configuration when some specified conditions are verified.

The conceptual designer wants to be able to compare different solutions of a design problem in a fair trade-off, which implicitly requires the possibility to predict the properties of *many different* concepts and configurations, in *early* stages of the design process.

Progress in aerospace will be based on new concepts and new configurations. Development costs are so high that single project failure can be disastrous for company sustainability. The designer must have the possibility to *move wide* (explore many concepts and variants) and *move deep* (predict specific final properties, answer many ‘what-if’ based on the limited amount of initially available information) in the design space. He can do this by integrating high level elementary solutions to global solutions and have their properties evaluated in a flexible way.

To facilitate the conceptual designer a KBE system should supply high level primitives, such as wing trunks, fuselage sections, power plant sections and landing gear sections (see some examples in figure 7), which can be instantiated and combined, both to represent the proposed solution and to analyse its specific properties. These properties can be compared to the requirements and, if necessary, the high level primitives can be re-instantiated to follow the designer’s thoughts of improvements. In addition, it should be easy to train the system or a system operator to add knowledge, in this case new high level primitives that are representing the newly created knowledge in the design process.

Fig.7: examples of high level primitives. Wing trunk, fuselage element, connection element, engine part.

DEVELOPMENT OF DESIGN AND ENGINEERING ENGINES

In order to take advantage of the KBE potential in conceptual design, a complex and integrated design support tool is created that can free the mind and time of creative designers to work on new paradigms. This design tool can be referred to as a Computational Design Engine [6] or as a Design and Engineering Engine, (DEE) [7]. Their basic skeleton is shown in figure 8. It should be clearly noted that DEE’s are used to support the designer in manipulating his ideas by modelling and analysis, not to take over his creative function, neither to super impose unfamiliar analysis environments.

The concept of the DEE’s is based on different developments in the field of management and IT. The management world provided the idea of family thinking as a concept to re-use production knowledge and equipment for larger product volumes. By identifying family similarities in different products and using flexible production units, the scale effect can be used for production cost reduction. IT is creating tools, programming environments based on artificial intelligence principles, that allow for the recording of the engineering intent behind a product design in rules. The rules combined with a proper set of data, can generate a family of products. Using the principle of object oriented thinking and programming [8], high-level primitives can be created in a generic programming environment to produce a specialized design support environment.

Fig. 8: paradigm of a Design and Engineering Engine.

The DEE can be seen as a high level object itself. It defines different methods (e.g. analysis tools) that can be applied to a specific class of objects. The class we want to work with on the conceptual aircraft design level is the aircraft. An instantiation of this class is built up from different high-level primitives. This compilation of primitives results in the so called product model, which actually represents the basic

knowledge carrier of the design. The methods to be applied on the class of products can be internal (built in the product model) and external methods. The currently available IT tools allow for programming of different tools inside the product model, however, most users would like to use the commercial tools available on the market like CFD and FE-packages, costs analysis tools etc., or in-house developed tools. The DEE should supply transparent bi-directional interfaces to these tools. In this way external methods are created to complete the class under consideration. These interfaces form one of the key issues for future development of DEE's.

DEE's can be created for different scales. After the aircraft conceptual design phase one wants to proceed with the preliminary design and the detail design. The detail design itself can be divided in the conceptual, preliminary and detail design phase for many of the aircraft subsystems. The DEE's should in the future allow for coupling of knowledge on different scales of the design. Starting from a certain design phase one would like to use the results of that phase as starting knowledge for the next one. Through proper coupling one could start at the conceptual phase and end at the detail definition. On each level the relevant methods, i.e. analysis tools, are included in the related DEE to incorporate multi-disciplinary, concurrent engineering.

The *rule based* parametric modeling part is the current main problem when creating DEE's, i.e. the creation of these high level primitives. If we want to perform aircraft multi-disciplinary design, analysis and optimization, we need rule based parametric models for these aircraft. Some initial research in this field was done in the horizontal aircraft chair, the Systems Integration Aircraft group of the Faculty. Some of the results will be discussed here.

Fig. 9: position of the ruled based parametric modeling in the design process

To show the position of the ruled based parametric modelling phase in the design process, figure 9 could be used. The top part of the figure shows the diverging character of the synthesis phase. Many potential solutions are generated for the design problem. In a subsequent converging process the different potential solutions should be analysed and a trade-off should be made to proceed to the next design level. To facilitate a proper trade-off, the design status of the different solutions should be at a same level. This is normally done through a first analysis and optimisation step. For this we need models of the different solutions to feed the different analysis tools. These models have to be updated several times during the optimisation, to incorporate improvements suggested by a designer or optimiser. This process is lengthy and costly due to the considerable amount of repetitive handwork required. Due to time and financial constraints, a pre-selection of the potential solutions is used to limit this effort; mature

in-house knowledge normally prevails on unproven and risky innovation, which, in many cases, leads to the elimination of such promising ideas. Quality and innovation cannot always benefit from this approach, whilst it is in this very phase that parametric modelling would help to broaden the explorable solution domain.

The current literature on multi-disciplinary design and optimization shows that true parametric modeling of complex products is not applied. Very complex optimization tools do optimization of very simple design solutions. This often leads to very well known parameter values. KBE allows the creation of parametric models of complex products through the implementation of fully rule based parametric high level primitives and a set of operations (addition, subtraction etc.) applicable to these primitives.

Fig. 10: examples of wing trunks [11].

An example of a high level primitive is the wing trunk [9], a building block that allows designers to build a parametric model of every part of the design that can be seen as a member of the family of aircraft parts with the function of creating aerodynamic forces. The external contour of all these parts is the basis for their appearance. The wing trunk parametric model allows for the specification of any number higher than one of these defining curves as a starting point. The

generative model, a name used in KBE to depict a model that can generate itself based on a set of input data, creates the external surfaces and the internal structure of the wing trunk based on all the input data given by the designer [10]. Some examples of wing trunks created in the KBE Environment ICAD, are shown in figure 10.

The generative model can add an instantiation of a wing trunk to other instantiations of the wing trunk, taking care of the proper connection of the external contours and the internal structure. With this primitive, a building block has been created with which a large range of aircraft wings, tails and movables (see example in figure 11) can be built or even a blended wing body aircraft

By adding a second primitive, the fuselage, a large range of aircraft can be modeled in a parametric way. This potential is shown in figure 12.

These simple examples show that the KBE tools are extremely powerful and allow the creation of DEE's. The results can be seen as proof of feasibility and give some assurance that any effort in further development of the DEE concept is useful and is likely to contribute to a solution for future scarcity of intellectual resources and virtual enterprises.

As stressed above, in order to support the designer in the exploration of his ideas, a proper link to

Fig.11: example of a movable surface [12].

different analysis tools is required. Some connection interfaces have been set up in order to extract knowledge from the product model and transfer analysis capability within the DEE. Knowledge engineering activities are required to incorporate in the product model also the specific knowledge for the control of the analysis tools. Creating robustness and generality to make sure that they work for a wide range of instantiations, is the major challenge for further development of these connections or interfaces.

Fig.12: examples of different aircraft configurations generated by the KBE system with the high level primitives approach [S.I.A. TU Delft].

A DEE FOR SMART MATERIAL APPLICATION ASSESSMENT

To conclude, an example for a simple DEE supporting the design of smart fuselage panels is shown. This DEE supports the design and implementation of smart materials for active noise reduction. This technology demands considerable analysis and several optimization steps to come up with feasible instantiations. When applying this technology, the use of trial and error is prohibitive.

An active noise control system consists out of monitoring sensors and controlling actuators based on piezo electric elements, which are mounted on the structure. The sensors pick up the vibration signal that is sent to an electric control unit, which determines the required input for the controlling actuators. A DEE is created that predicts the transfer functions of panels. The transfer functions consist out of specified responses to predefined impulse signals. With these transfer functions transmission loss predicting algorithms, developed and patented by TNO TPD*, can be calibrated and consequently the transmission loss of the panel under consideration can be predicted. An overview of the DEE is given in figure 13.

Fig. 13: the smart panel design and analysis DEE.

Fig.14: Finite element model of a panel with 9 piezo electric elements. All the piezo electric elements shown are loaded by an electrical charge.

The DEE starts like the previously discussed DEE for aircraft with an ICAD model generator. This model generator generates the FEM model of the panel including the piezo electric actuators and/or sensors starting from a set of input parameters such as panel thickness, material properties, position and dimensions of the piezo electric elements etc. [13].

Fig. 15: The two fuselage primitives: floor and the fuselage skin panels (the air, frames and stringers are included).

Together with the load case definition, which also can be specified in the input parameter set, the complete input file for the FEM package ABAQUS is automatically generated by the model generator. An example of an ICAD generated meshed panel model with nine piezo electric actuators is shown in figure 14.

The meshed model is analysed with the FEM package ABAQUS. Different types of analyses, that support piezo electric analysis, are available: static analysis, eigenmode analysis and modal dynamic analysis.

The Smart Panel DEE is capable of handling the active noise control technique on panel level. The next step is to update this DEE to a fuselage DEE.

All elements that are present in a fuselage and are of importance for the sound transmission loss through the fuselage wall have to be represented in the fuselage model. First of all the structural elements

have to be present in the fuselage model. Two basic concepts are considered. Namely the conventional stiffened shell concept, which consists out of the skin, frames and stringers, and the sandwich monocoque concept. It should be possible to model hybrids of these two concepts.

The fuselage that has to be modelled with the fuselage DEE can be considered to consist out of two fuselage primitives as is shown in figure 15. These primitives are additional to the ones defined for the aircraft DEE. The first and most important one is the fuselage skin panel primitive. It consists out of a skin, which can be a sandwich or a normal skin with frames and stringers. Furthermore, if required, the space on the inside of this part can be modelled as air and/or a small layer of this space as insulation blankets by specifying the proper material properties. By positioning two skin panel primitives 'inside each other', double walls like the skin with interior panel can be created (see figure 16). The second primitive is simply the floor panel with reinforcement beams.

Using these two primitives many different fuselage concepts can be generated and the effect of smart material application on sound transmission studied. Two arbitrary examples are shown in figure 17.

Fig.16: Meshed model of a fuselage testbed consisting out of the skin, 24 stringers and 9 frames. No end rings are included

Fig.17: Examples of two eigenmodes of the fuselage testbed. (a) The radial-axial 1,3 cylinder mode and (b) a sub panel mode superimposed on a radial-axial 0,2 cylinder mode.

REFERENCES

1. N.F.M. Roozenburg, J. Eekels; *Product Design: fundamentals and methods*; Chichester: Wiley; 1995
2. J. Pora; *Composite materials in the Airbus A380-From History to Future*; proceedings ICCM-13, Beijing, China; 2001
3. A. Beukers, E. Van Hinte; *Lightness*; 010 Publisher, Rotterdam 1998.
4. M.J.L. van Tooren; *Composite fuselage design: fiction or reality*; proceedings ICCM-13, Beijing, China; 2001
5. S. Cooper, I. Fan, G. Li; *Achieving Competitive Advantage through Knowledge-Based engineering; Document prepared for the Department of Trade and Industry*, 2001.
6. A. J. Morris; *MOB A European Distributed Multi-Disciplinary Design and Optimisation Project*; AIAA 2002 conference, Atlanta, GA, USA, September 2002, AIAA-2002-5444.
7. M.J.L. van Tooren, L. Krakkers, G. La Rocca, A. Beukers; *Design and Technology in Aerospace, Flying High*; Onderzoek Integraal Ontwerpen Architectuur & Techniek, Verliefdheid of Hartstocht; April 2002.
8. P. F. Drucker, I. Nonaka et alii; *Harvard Business Review on Knowledge Management*; Harvard Business School Press, 1998.
9. G. La Rocca, L. Krakkers, M.J.L. van Tooren; *Description of the ICAD BWB-surface generator code*; report MOB/6/TUD/D6.2ia; December 2002
10. G. La Rocca, L. Krakkers, M.J.L. van Tooren; *Description of the ICAD BWB-structure generator code*; report MOB/6/TUD/D6.2ib; December 2002.
11. G. La Rocca, L. Krakkers, M.J.L. van Tooren; *Development of an ICAD Generative Model for Blended Wing Body Aircraft design*; AIAA 2002 conference, Atlanta, GA, USA, September 2002, AIAA-2002-5447.
12. T. van Laan; *ThermoCompas: thermoplastic composite primary aircraft structure*; internal report, P.T., TU Delft; March 2001.
13. L.A., Krakkers, M.J.L., van Tooren, A. Beukers; *A design engine to evaluate sound damping of flat panels in the low frequency range*; ECCM-10 proceedings, Brugge (Belgium); June 2002.